

COMPUTATIONALLY EFFICIENT FE MICROMECHANICAL MODELLING OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES UNDER LONGITUDINAL LOADING

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COMPRESSIVE FAILURE OF UD COMPOSITES

Composite's compressive strength is dependent on microstructural imperfections: fibre waviness, voids, and notches.

Need to study at microscale level:

- **Local microstructural imperfections guide yielding, fibre kinking, and failure response.**

REAL MICROSTRUCTURES – A REPRESENTATIVE VOLUME

A typical microstructure contains the following geometrical imperfections:

An RVE length of **1500 μm** and a cross section of **200 μm x 200 μm** is required to capture a truly Representative Volume Element (RVE).

This size leads to a volume which contains hundreds of fibres (> 600).

MODELLING COMPRESSION IN UD COMPOSITES

Different FE-model approaches in literature for fibre kinking:

Single-fibre RVE with PBCs

Multi-fibre RVE with PBCs

Single array of fibres RVE without PBCs

Multi-fibre RVE from CT scans without PBCs

A hybrid micro-macromechanical RVE

However, none of the available models are capable to account the statistical variability needed for a representative microstructure.

Researchers highlight the issue of computational cost using such models.

OUTLINE

Reduce computational cost of micromechanical FE-Models to enable truly representative RVEs (RVEs > 600 fibres)

- **Concept**
- **New approach – Shell-Beam models**
- **Application to multifibre scale**
- **Conclusions**

REDUCTION OF COMPLEXITY

The key mechanisms during fibre kinking are :

Bending stresses acting on the Fibre

Shear stresses experienced by the Matrix

Analytical models correlate with FE-models at single fibre scale confirming these mechanisms (Fleck et al. 1995, Morais and Marques 1997, Pimenta et al. 2009, and others).

(Pimenta et al. 2009)

We can reduce the complexity of the FE-models and element dimensionality aiming to improve computational efficiency!

MODELS IN TENSION

Many numerical models in tension employ computationally efficient elements to represent key mechanisms.

Spring Element Method

Fibres: Longitudinal tensile **springs**
Matrix: Transverse shear **springs**

Limitation :

- **Straight fibres in all models**

FE- micromechanical models

Fibres: **Truss** elements
Matrix: **Continuum** elements
Connection: **Kinematic constraints**

Limitation :

- **Straight fibres**
- **Square packing**

Our Approach at unit cell level

Replace computationally heavy continuum elements with more efficient alternatives !

**Reduction of the number of DoFs of the FE-model
+
Reduction of the expected simulation time**

CONTINUUM-BEAM (CB) MODEL

- Fibres \rightarrow Compression + Bending \rightarrow Beam Elements

VS

CONTINUUM-BEAM (CB) MODEL

- Fibres \rightarrow Compression + Bending \rightarrow Beam Elements

- 92 % reduction in simulation time.
- CB Models** cannot reach representative RVE size, i.e., 600 fibres.

SHELL-BEAM (SB) MODEL

Shells can replace continuum elements and experience shear.

Spring Element Method

SHELL-BEAM (SB) MODEL

Main challenge when using shells: account for the non uniform stress and strain distribution of the 3D volume.

Baseline

SB_s

SB_k

SHELL-BEAM (SB_K) MODEL

We can ensure equivalent fibre-kinking by calibrating the shear stresses of the matrix assuming equilibrium of moments at the edges of the RVE

Fibre volume fraction

Calibration of stresses :

$$M^{3D} = M^{SB}$$

SHELL-BEAM (SB_k) MODEL

- Matrix \rightarrow Shear \rightarrow Shell elements

- SB_k Model vs Baseline model:

- ✓ Great predictive power (< 4% error).
- ✓ Great improvement in efficiency (~ 99.5 % reduction).
- ✓ Target RVE size (< 11 hours)

SHELL-BEAM (SB_s) MODEL

Apart from:

1. Calibration of shell thickness
2. Calibration shear stresses (equilibrium of moments)

Fibres need to behave the same way as in baseline case.

Compatibility of rotations ensures the fibres kink in the same way as the baseline model.

Calibration of strains

$$\theta^{3D} = \theta^{SB}$$

$$\gamma_{xy}^{3D} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \left(1 + \frac{D_f}{h_m^{3D}}\right) \theta^{3D}$$

Baseline

$$\gamma_{xy}^{SB} = \left(1 + \frac{D_f}{h_m^{SB}}\right) \theta^{SB}$$

SB_s

SHELL-BEAM (SB_s) MODEL

- Matrix + Fibres \rightarrow Remove kinematic constraints \rightarrow Merged nodes

- SB_s Model** vs **Baseline** model:

- ✓ Good predictive power (< 11% error).
- ✓ Great improvement in efficiency (~ 99.6 % reduction).
- ✓ Target RVE size (< 10 hours)

Application on real microstructures

Assessment of computational cost on real microstructures from CT images*

Baseline

SB_K

SB_s

REAL MICROSTRUCTURES

REAL MICROSTRUCTURES – COMPUTATIONAL COST

○ **Baseline Model**

○ **SB_k Model**

○ **SB_s Model**

- Maximum plastic shear strains in the matrix occur in similar locations in the RVE.

	Stiffness (% error)	Strength (% error)	Simulation time (% reduction)
Baseline	-	-	113 hours (-)
SB_k	- 0.3 %	+ 6.4 %	~ 3 min (99.997 %)
SB_s	- 0.4 %	+ 8.9 %	~ 2 min (99.999 %)

CONCLUSIONS & SUMMARY

Challenges

1. Computational cost
2. Creation of truly real microstructures
3. Not large enough RVEs

Proposed SB Models

Error in strength: **< 9 % (SB)**
Improvement in simulation time:
>99.99 %

Applications

- What are the key features trigger fibre kinking (e.g., fibre misalignment or fibre waviness)?
- Which parameter dictates failure (e.g., fibre misalignment or voids/cracks)?
- How can we improve compressive strength?

- Expand to longitudinal tension.
- Expand to short-fibre composites.

Next COMP

Next Generation
Fibre-Reinforced Composites

<https://nextcomp.ac.uk>

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